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Optical Absorption and Electron Spin Resonance Spectral Studies of Copper(II) Hydroxy Ketone and Aldehyde Complexes in different Solvents

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THE present communication deals with the optical absorption and electron spin resonance studies of copper(II) complexes of hydroxy aromatic ketones and aldehydes, viz. 2-hydroxyacetophenone, resacetophenone, peonol and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde in different solvents, i.e. dioxane, dimethylformamide, pyridine and piperidine to find out solute-solvent interaction and to determine the nature of bonding in the complexes.

Experimental

The copper(II) complexes of 2-hydroxyacetophenone, resacetophenone, 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone (peonol) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde were prepared according to the procedures described in the literature¹. Spectroscopic grade dioxane, dimethylformamide, pyridine and piperidine were used as solvents. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer and esr spectra (at room temperature 300 K) on a Varian E-4 X band spectrometer employing 1.25–2 gauss modulation and operating at a frequency of 9.6 GHz in different solvents at a concentration of 10^{-3} M, using DPPH as the g-marker.

Results and Discussion

The Cu^{II} complexes of 2-hydroxyacetophenone, resacetophenone, peonol, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde are coloured powders, insoluble in water but soluble in dioxane, dimethylformamide, pyridine and piperidine. All the complexes are stable in air and non-hygroscopic. Analytical data indicate that the ratio of ligand to copper is 2 : 1. Molar conductance values in nitrobenzene indicate that all the complexes are non-electrolytes in nature.

The optical absorption spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes in dioxane, dimethylformamide, pyridine, piperidine show intense charge transfer and free ligand absorption bands in the region 400–450 nm. The absorption spectra also consist of broad absorption *d-d* transitions of Cu^{II} in the tetragonal field at 14 920–15 250 cm⁻¹. The absorption band of the Cu^{II} complexes pertaining to the transition ²B_{1g} → ²E_g is lowered and appears at 14 920–15 250 cm⁻¹ in these solvents (Table 1). This lowering can be attributed to the interaction of the solvent molecules with copper(II) along the Z-axis and the extent of lowering may be taken as a measure of the donor strength of the solvent which falls in the order, dioxane < dimethylformamide < pyridine < piperidine.

In solid-state, the four-coordinated copper(II) complexes of 2-hydroxyacetophenone, resacetophenone, peonol and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde are transformed in solution into six-coordinated tetragonally distorted octahedral complexes in view of the solvent interaction with copper. Comparison of the absorption maximum values suggest that the distortion is in the order, dioxane > dimethylformamide > pyridine > piperidine, indicating that the coordinating ability of the solvents is in the reverse order. This is in agreement with the observation made by the earlier investigators².

Esr spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes in dioxane, dimethylformamide and pyridine at a concentration of 10^{-3} M consist of four absorption lines. These four lines in the multiplet correspond to the (2I+1=4) spin orientations of the copper nuclei with I=3/2. Esr spectra of the most copper(II) complexes in solution at room temperature normally

TABLE I

Copper complex of	Solvents	$\lambda_{\max}$ cm^{-1}	$\langle g_o \rangle$	$\langle A_o \rangle$ $\times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	α^2	K
o-Hydroxyacetophenone	Dioxane	15 220	2.06	74	0.090 0	0.263 2
	DMF	15 200	2.09	73	0.156 7	0.290 5
	Pyridine	15 120	2.10	71	0.181 5	0.294 9
	Piperidine	15 038	—	—	—	—
Resacetophenone	Dioxane	15 250	2.07	72	0.110 9	0.271 4
	DMF	15 220	2.09	70	0.158 7	0.282 2
	Pyridine	15 150	2.11	67	0.207 1	0.293 8
	Piperidine	15 038	—	—	—	—
Peonol	Dioxane	15 150	2.07	73	0.110 2	0.270 5
	DMF	15 140	2.10	70	0.181 9	0.292 2
	Pyridine	15 105	2.12	69	0.229 0	0.309 3
	Piperidine	15 020	—	—	—	—
2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde	Dioxane	15 150	2.07	72	0.110 9	0.271 4
	DMF	15 120	2.09	68	0.160 0	0.272 6
	Pyridine	14 950	2.12	61	0.234 0	0.287 3
	Piperidine	14 920	—	—	—	—

exhibit four hyperfinelines with spin dependent line widths due to the tumbling motion of the micro-crystalline units. This tumbling motion in solution will average the anisotropic g and A values observed in the solids. The values of $\langle g \rangle$ for the Cu^{II} complexes of hydroxy aldehydes and ketones are slightly greater in pyridine and dimethylformamide than in dioxane (Table 1). The $\langle g \rangle$ values are in the order, pyridine $\rangle$ dimethylformamide $\rangle$ dioxane, which indicate that the pyridine and dimethylformamide interact to a greater extent than dioxane. This is also evident from the shift of optical absorption peaks to a lower frequency side in the electronic spectra of these complexes.

The $\langle A \rangle$ values of the copper(II) hydroxy ketone and aldehyde complexes showed lower values in pyridine and dimethylformamide than dioxane (Table 1). The variation of the splitting with the solvent thus indicates that the stronger the solvated complex, the smaller is the value of the unpaired electron's wave function at the nucleus. Apparently the bonding solvent pulls the electron away from the copper.

In a spectrum recorded in solution the isotropic nuclear hyperfine splitting $\langle A \rangle$ is related to the covalence of the unpaired electron by the equation,

$$\langle A \rangle = p(-\alpha^2 k_o + g - 2.0023 + \text{smaller terms})$$

where α^2 is the fraction of time the unpaired electron is on the copper atom, p is 0.036 cm^{-1} and K_o is about 0.43. The α^2 values for the above complexes in the given solvents indicate that the bonding is quite covalent in nature and is delocalised over the copper and ligand orbitals. The α^2 values are higher in pyridine than in dimethylformamide and dioxane (Table 1) which is a result of the donation of charge by the solvent molecules along with the Z-axis to the central copper ion. The donation of electrons to the copper from the axial ligand causes a back-donation to the inplane-ligands, which results in an increase in α^2 values in pyridine.

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Synthesis, Characterisation and Electrical Properties of Coordination Polymers of Copper(II) and Zinc(II) with Polyhydroxyquinones

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THE dihydroxyquinones are capable of being tetra-functional and form linear polymers when allowed to react with suitable metal ions. Singh *et al.*¹ reported the synthesis and characterisation of a few metal chelate polymers with 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone. We report here the synthesis and characterisation of coordination polymers of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone (DHBQ), 5,8-dihydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (DHNQ), 2,3,5,6-tetrahydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone (THBQ) and 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (DHAQ). The order of the